

Identification of inorganic and organic species of arsenic in some water plant samples

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Abstract : Arsenic speciation analysis in water plant samples was measured by Ion exchange Chromatography (IC) with ICP-MS detection. Separation of four arsenic species As(III), dimethyl arsenic acid (DMA), monomethyl arsenic acid (MMA) was achieved using ion exchange column, SUPP1, with isocratic elution at pH 8.3. The entire separation was performed in 900 s. The IC-ICPMS detection limit for four arsenic species were in the range of 0.02–0.04 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ based on the procedure¹. This method was successfully applied to water plant samples like Water Hyacinth and Hydrilla. Leaching behavior of different arsenic species from Water Hyacinth and Hydrilla were studied using different extractants, water and NH_4NO_3 . Quantification of each individual arsenic species were calculated from the calibration curve obtained from standard arsenic solutions.

Keywords : Arsenic speciation, ICP-MS, Water Hyacinth and Hydrilla.

Introduction

Arsenic is a well-known toxic element, and it is also known that the toxicity is carried with the degree of methylation. Thus, the toxicity tends to decrease in the order, arsenous acid (As(III)) > arsenic acid or arsenate (As(V)) > monomethyl arsenic acid (MMA) = dimethyl arsenic acid (DMA) > trimethylated species (Arsenobetaine (AsB)) etc. and their structures are shown in Fig. 1. The World Health Organisation (WHO) level of arsenic in drinking water is $10 \mu\text{L}^{-1}$. The arsenic limits refer to total arsenic, which makes a compelling need of regulation based on individual arsenic compounds. Speciation analysis of arsenic usually requires the coupling of proper sample preparation with two analytical techniques : first to separate the chemical forms of arsenic, and second, a sensitive means of detection of inorganic forms of arsenic. The inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) detector has been employed for almost two decades and provides best level of sensitivity. The ICP-MS detector, when coupled with high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), offers the versatility of analysis for both organic and inorganic arsenic compound. ICP-MS has become the favored detection technique for speciation analysis. In ICP-MS, the high

Fig. 1. Structure of arsenic species.

efficiency of atomization and ion formation of the inductively coupled plasma (ICP) is coupled with the specific and sensitive detection capability offered by the mass spectrometry.

HPLC has the advantage of performing separations of non-volatile species, thus it has greater versatility over gas chromatography which often requires derivatization

of analytes before analysis. HPLC has an inherent characteristic of reproducibility of separation. Two of the earliest example of HPLC being coupled to ICP-MS were by Thompson and Houk² and Dean *et al.*³. In arsenic speciation analysis, ion exchange chromatography is the most extensively used method followed closely by the ion-pair chromatography. In the early work of arsenic speciation using HPLC-MS, Beauchemin *et al.*⁴ studied both ion-exchange and reverse phase ion-pairing chromatography. The other separation modes of chromatography (i.e. reverse phase and size exclusion) are often used for other general elemental speciation analysis but the majority of work utilizes ion exchange or ion pair chromatography for arsenic speciation analysis.

Present project aims to investigate the inorganic and organic species of arsenic in water plant samples and their extraction behavior in water and NH_4NO_3 medium. Effort has been made to quantify the different arsenic species in different water plant samples.

Experimental

Samples : Water Hyacinth and Hydrilla were taken for investigation of leaching behavior of different species of inorganic and organic arsenic. The samples were collected from Jayanti Sarovar, Jamshedpur, Jharkhand, India.

Different extraction modules were used to extract arsenic from Water Hyacinth and Hydrilla and different species of arsenic in these water plant samples were identified and quantified. The extraction solution of 5 mM NH_4NO_3 and distilled water were used to extract arsenic using horizontal room temperature shaker for 24 h. For centrifugation a Eppendorf centrifuge instrument, 5804, was employed.

For the determination of different species of arsenic concentrations, Inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometer (ICP-MS) (Perkin-Elmer model elan DRC) system hyphenated with Ion Chromatography unit (Metrohm) were used. The sample introduction system of the ICP-MS consisted of a micro-concentric nebulizer and a Scott type spray chamber. The torch was equipped with a shield.

Sampler and skimmer cones were made from nickel. For anion exchange chromatography SUPP1, Metrohm analytical column was used in the systems.

Stock solutions with concentrations of 10 ppm of arsenite, arsenate, dimethylarsinic acid and monomethylarsonic acid were used for the preparation of standard solutions.

Water Hyacinth and Hydrilla were dried and ground in Mixer Grinder to a particle size below 0.25 mm. The material was stored at room temperature in a plastic bottle. All the solutions were prepared by Millipore ultra pure water.

For the determination of extraction of different arsenic species, comparison has been made using different extraction solutions. The ratio of Water Hyacinth/Hydrilla and the extraction solution was kept in the ratio of 1 : 50. Two set of Water Hyacinth along with extraction solution (water and NH_4NO_3) were kept in a room temperature shaker for 24 h. Similarly another two set of Hydrilla were kept for 24 h with same extraction solutions. After the completion of extraction process, the supernatant solution was kept in a 5 ml capacity of centrifuge vials and the solution was centrifuged at 5000 rpm for 5 min. The centrifuged solution was transferred in sample vials of ion chromatogram for the speciation analysis.

A gradient programme was used to analyze all the extracts IC-ICPMS using Metrohm SUPP1 chromatographic column. The mobile phase consists of 5 mM NH_4NO_3 and 50 mM NH_4NO_3 . Table 2 shows the Gradient programme for arsenic speciation analysis. Mobile phase flow rate influences the efficiency of separation of the arsenic compounds. In the present study flow rate was kept constant at 1.0 ml min^{-1} . Arsenic mixed standards consisting As(III), As(V), monomethyl arsenic acid (MMA) and dimethyl arsenic acid (DMA) were prepared with concentration of 10 ppb, 20 ppb and 50 ppb by proper dilution from stock solution. The arsenic species studied As(III), As(V), MMA and DMA were separated and detected by IC-ICPMS using the operation conditions given in Table 1. The analysis of arsenic species was completed in less than 900 s using a step gradient

Table 1. Instrumental parameters of ICP-MS and HPLC

ICP-MS	
RF power (Watt)	1200
Nebulisation gas flow (L/min)	0.84
Auxiliary argon flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	
Coolant argon flow rate (L min ⁻¹)	
Sample uptake rate (ml/min)	1.0
Chromatographic system	
Analytical column	SUPP1
Mobile phase	Buffer (A) : 5 mM NH ₄ NO ₃ , 2% (v/v) methanol, pH 8.3 Elution buffer (B) : 50 mM NH ₄ NO ₃ , 2% (v/v) methanol, pH 8.3
Flow rate (ml min ⁻¹)	1.0
Injection volume (μL)	100

Table 2. Gradient programme

Time in min	A	B
0.00	100	0
4.5	90	10
8.0	30	70
10.0	20	80
10.5	90	10
12.5	100	0

showed in Table 2 The analytical peaks obtained were evaluated in terms of peak area by calibration method (between 5 to 20 ppb).

Results

The chromatographic separation obtained for the four arsenic species studied are illustrated in Fig. 2. Calibration curve were made for individual species of arsenic and presented in Fig. 2 (a, b, c and d). The results of the calibration curve indicated good linearity (R₂ = 0.97-0.99) in most of the cases.

Based on the optimized condition of IC-ICPMS, separation of arsenic species, As(III), DMA, MMA and As(V) were attained in two different water plant samples like, Water Hyacinth and Hydrilla as shown in the chromatogram (Fig. 3 and Fig. 4). The leaching behavior of two different extraction medium, water and 5 mM NH₄NO₃, were reported.

The chromatogram showed the presence of one unknown species which was merged with the As(III) species for both the plant samples. Proper separation of these two peaks will be carried out in future to arrive at any

Fig. 2. Chromatogram of different species of arsenic in arsenic mixed standard solution.

Fig. 3. Calibration graph with reference to (a) As(III), (b) DMA, (c) MMA and As(V).

Fig. 4. Chromatogram of arsenic speciation in water Hyacinth plant (a) and Hydrilla plants (b) after water extraction.

Fig. 5. Chromatogram of arsenic speciation in NH_4NO_3 extraction of Hyacinth plant (a) and Hydrilla plants (b).

Table 3. Concentration of As species in Water Hyacinth and Hydrilla Plant samples after extraction in water and NH_4NO_3 medium

Sample	As conc. (ppb)			
	As(III)	DMA	MMA	As(v)
Water extract				
Water Hyacinth	Merged with unknown peak	0.20	0.50	4.90
Hydrilla	Merged with unknown peak	n.f.	0.50	4.75
NH_4NO_3 extract				
Water Hyacinth	Merged with unknown peak	n.f.	0.47	6.70
Hydrilla	Merged with unknown peak	n.f.	n.f.	0.56

n.f. = not found

conclusion. Since the Reference materials for these compounds are not commercially available, their possible presence in plants extract was investigated by analyzing under same condition of plant samples as measured for

standard solutions of arsenic species. It is difficult to identify the unknown peak because of unavailability of proper reference materials. Effort was made to quantify the individual species of As from the calibration curve and reported in Table 3. It was apparent from Table 3 that in most of the cases DMA is below the detection limit. As(v) concentration was considerably high compare to the other arsenic species obtained from different extractant solutions.

References

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